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D1.3 – Ethics Report, Year 1

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Glossary of terms

Item	Description
CA	Consortium Agreement
DEP	Digital Europe Programme
DPA	Data Processing Agreement
EC	European Commission
EIA	Ethical Impact Assessment
EU	European Union
EDPB	European Data Protection Board
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
The Consortium Project's Partners	All the Project Partners, viz. TU DELFT + Trust-IT + COMMpla + EAAE + ICF + IW
The Project Beneficiaries	The signatory Partners of the Grant Agreement, viz. TU DELFT + Trust-IT + EAAE + ICF + IW
TWG	Thematic Working Groups
Y1	Year 1 of the digiNEB.eu project, i.e. the period October 2022 – Sep. 2023

Keywords

Data management; privacy; ethics; privacy policy; data processing roles.

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Executive Summary

The “Ethics Report, Year 1” provides a comprehensive analysis of the ethical considerations and implications associated with the digiNEB.eu project during its first year of implementation. As digital technologies continue to shape the way we interact, share information, and collaborate, ensuring ethical practices becomes paramount.

This report highlights key aspects related to intellectual property, data protection, user engagement, content management, and legal documentation, such as the Terms of Use and the website Privacy Policy. Key legal aspects which the digiNEB.eu project should consider are discussed, and relevant suggestions provided. Ethical considerations are explored, which primarily relate to legal data protection aspects.

A number of legal and ethical aspects to be considered by the Project’s Partners following this first-year internal review have been raised, and relevant potential solutions have been suggested. Some of those have been already implemented in Year 1, whereas others will be tackled in the period January 2024 through September 2024 (Year 2).

A revised version (Year 2) of this report will be prepared in September 2024, accounting for 12 more months of project activities.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope

The purpose and scope of this deliverable is to provide an overview of ethical and legal data protection as well as intellectual property considerations inherent to the digiNEB.eu project (“Project”) following careful analysis of the Project’s website, activities, Terms of Use, and Privacy Policy. This exercise is relevant as it permits the Project, which has as its objective the creation of bridges between science, art, technology, and culture, to address societal issues through collaborative processes, as well as to create bridges between different disciplines and, more generally, fostering participation on multiple levels.

Compliance with ethical standards and best practices in the area of digital technologies is increasingly relevant in our data-driven society. In order to promote and embody the values of the European Union and the European Commission, which funds this project, ethical evaluations of EU projects are of paramount importance. For this reason, an Ethics Advisor, Prof. Dr. Paolo Balboni, has been appointed and tasked with carrying out such evaluations of the Project. This deliverable, D1.3 Ethics Report, Y1, contains relevant considerations from both the legal and ethical perspectives, which the Project’s Partners need to consider in order to ensure that the Project acts in compliance with legal and ethical standards.

Furthermore, it is important to highlight that all ethical and data protection considerations presented in this deliverable by the External Advisor are brought to the attention of the digiNEB.eu Ethics Board. Established in September 2023 and chaired by the External Advisor, the board comprises the following members: Michele Nannipieri (Trust-IT DPO), Erik van Leeuwen (TU Delft DPO, also representing EAAE), and Janine Strandberg (TU Delft Data Steward). Other project members also support the Board by providing pertinent information related to the project and its activities. The Board convened twice in September, on the 7th and 13th, and is scheduled to meet quarterly to oversee the implementation of the present deliverable's recommendations.

1.2 Structure of the document

The structure of the document is as follows:

- Section 2 of the deliverable provides considerations regarding the intellectual property aspects of the Project, with specific reference to the content that is made available on the Project’s website. Some additional considerations are expressed around the actions that the Project should consider to ensure that the content/material/results generated in the context of the Project are duly protected (to the extent that such content constitutes the object of copyright protection) by choosing the most appropriate form of protection and by ensuring that the ownership of those results is clearly defined among the different Project’s Partners.
- Section 3 provides an overview of the main data protection implications that arise from the Project and, in particular, from the Project’s website. Some recommendations are therefore expressed with the purpose of ensuring that the different processing activities carried out in the context of the Project are performed in compliance with the applicable data protection principles.
- Section 4 deals with ethical concerns in relation to the Project. In particular, it highlights the necessity to ensure legal compliance, with specific reference to data protection, in order to also ensure that best practices from the field of ethics are incorporated into the activities of the Project.

- Section 5 provides recommendations which will be taken into consideration in the coming months by the Project's Partners to ensure further compliance with relevant legal aspects that are discussed in the deliverable.
- Section 6 sets out the main conclusion reached throughout this deliverable.

1.3. Relation with other project deliverables

The following deliverables of digiNEB.eu are closely related to this document:

- D1.1 "Project Handbook" (V1.0 published in December 2022)
- D1.2 "Data Management Plan" (V1.0 published in February 2023)
- D1.4 "Ethics Report, Y2" (Expected to be published in M24, i.e. August 2024)

2. Intellectual Property Considerations

2.1 Overview of intellectual property aspects in digiNEB.eu

The present section of the deliverable provides considerations regarding the intellectual property aspects of the Project, with specific reference to the content that is made available on the Project's website.

From an intellectual property perspective, the sections of the website where content is uploaded / can be uploaded by external users are analysed so as to identify potential infringements that may arise from the use of protected work/material. Guidelines on the actions to be taken in order to ensure that such work/material is used in compliance with the applicable legal requirements provided (mainly represented in the Italian legal Framework by Law No. 633 of 22 April 1941) are also provided.

As for the material that is protected by intellectual property rights, it should be noted that, as a rule, this can only be used with the prior authorisation of the right holder (typically by means of a "license" agreement or by means of a "transfer" agreement), unless exceptions apply. For the purposes of the Project, it is worth mentioning that some exceptions to the rules set out under the applicable copyright legislation may be considered in some limited situations, such as the case where citations and reproductions of a protected work are carried out for criticism or discussion purposes (if they are not in competition with economic use of the original work) or for teaching or scientific research purposes (if they only take place for illustrative purposes and not for commercial purposes), as set out under Article 70 of Law no. 633 of 22 April 1941, along with its various amendments. It is possible that the Project may be able to rely, in some limited situations (e.g., in the context of e-learning courses), on the exceptions provided by Law No. 633 of 22 April 1941, although reliance on these exceptions should be carefully assessed considering that these exceptions tend to be interpreted narrowly by the courts (as they deviate from the general rules)

2.1 Analysis of the different sections of the website

For the purpose of the present analysis, the following sections of the website are analysed so as to identify potential legal concerns (mainly from a copyright perspective but also, where relevant, from a data protection and contractual perspective) that may arise from the upload/display of the content in those sections (either by Trust-IT, technical coordinator and data controller or by other Project's partners, as well as website users that have registered an account on the Project's website). Namely, these include the Digital Toolkit, Success Stories, and the e-learning platforms. This section looks at each of these three types of content.

2.2.1 Digital Toolkit

The Digital Toolkit contains different types of information sheets that present software, forms, and applications which may be useful to industry and policy makers. An example is available here: <https://digiNEB.eu/digital-toolkit/alert-system-v2>. There are three ways in which these information sheets (i.e. web pages dedicated to each tool) are generated:

- Project Partners find information and develop the information sheets themselves or
- Project Partners invite owners/developers of the tools/software/modules to propose and upload their own information sheets upon registration, as in a marketplace;
- Owners/developers of tools/software /modules independently visit the Project website on their own, without any invitation, register, and upload the information sheets.

In all cases, due attention should be placed on the following:

- Pictures/images and other content/material presented in this section of the website that are likely to be protected by intellectual property rights (or that may otherwise be protected by the applicable legislation, such as in the case of registered trademarks).

- Hyperlinks to the website of the relevant software/tool (with the result that, when clicking on these hyperlinks, internet users are redirected to those pages which may contain protected work under copyright / intellectual property law).

As for pictures/images and other content/material presented in this section of the website, it should be recalled (as mentioned above) that material that is protected by intellectual property rights can, in principle, only be used with the prior authorisation of the right holder, unless exceptions apply. In light of this, it is recommended that the following actions are undertaken in order to limit the risk that the posting of content/material in the Digital Toolkit section of the website may amount to a copyright infringement:

- Contacting the owner of the third parties' website so as to seek their specific authorisation to reproduce content/material that is available on their website (to the extent that this is, in fact, protected by copyright) in the Project's website and to ensure that this material/content is used in compliance with the conditions set out by the right holder, in terms (e.g.) of the duration for which the license is granted, obligations around attribution (e.g., the obligation to identify the creator of the licensed material and of displaying a copyright notice), etc.
- Verifying whether the owner of the relevant website (e.g., the developer's website) has included any specific provisions in its Terms of Service / of Use of their website limiting the possibility for third parties to insert hyperlinks to their website (and, if so, refrain from posting a clickable link to the work that has been illegally published if the Project has knowledge/suspect of this illegality).¹

With specific reference to the use of hyperlinks to external websites, it is reasonable to maintain that a similar redirection can be lawfully implemented without the authorisation of the right holder to the extent that the protected work has been (legally) made available on a freely accessible basis on another website² (although the owner of the website may choose to set out limitations in the Terms of Use of its own website on the possibility for third party to insert such hyperlinks). A different conclusion would, however, be reached in case the Project is aware (or should have been aware) of the fact that the website to which it wishes to redirect its users includes content that has been illegally published (e.g. because it has been notified of this by the right holder). In a similar situation, the Project should, in fact, refrain from posting a clickable link to the work that has been illegally published to avoid the risk of assuming liabilities for copyright infringement.³ Moreover (and from a broader perspective), considering that the website includes several links to third parties' websites in this section (as well as in other sections of the website), it is advisable that the Terms of Use also includes a reference to the fact that Trust-IT S.r.l. ("Trust-IT") has no control over the nature and the content of those third parties' websites, that the use of those websites is regulated by the specific terms set out therein by the owner of those websites, and that Trust-IT has no liability for any loss or damage that may arise from their use. A similar recommendation has already been expressed by the External Advisor in the context of some previous interactions established with the Project, following which the

¹ Based on the case-law mentioned above, it is worth noting that knowledge of the illegality of the publication is presumed if those hyperlinks are provided for profit, although this does not seem to be the case for the project.

² Based on the case-law of the Court of Justice of the European Union, in a similar situation, the "act of communication to the public" that is performed by the project by including these links to its website would not be directed at a "new" public, meaning a public that was not initially taken into account by the copyright holders at the time the initial communication was authorized.

<https://curia.europa.eu/juris/document/document.jsf?docid=147847&mode=req&pageIndex=1&dir=&occ=firs t&part=1&text=&doclang=EN&cid=2120171> ;

<https://curia.europa.eu/jcms/upload/docs/application/pdf/2014-02/cp140020en.pdf>

³ <https://curia.europa.eu/jcms/upload/docs/application/pdf/2016-09/cp160092en.pdf>.

Terms of Use have, in fact, been revised so as to include – in the “Liability” clause of the website’s Terms of Use – a specific reference to the content contained in third-party websites.

In addition to the above, in order to ensure that third parties that upload content/material in the Digital Toolkit section (such as the developers/owners of a given software/solution that have set up an account on the Project’s website) hold the necessary rights/authorisations for uploading and sharing such content, it is recommended that the Project:

- Seek specific reassurances from the website users (when uploading content/material within the website) that they have the right to post/upload such content and that such content does not violate the intellectual property rights of third parties);
- Where the relevant content/material that is uploaded by external parties on this section of the website is protected by intellectual property rights, enter into a license /sub-license agreement with those users under which users grant to the Project a license to reproduce, make available, and display such content (the specific extent of such license can then be defined – e.g., this can be made non-exclusive, royalty-free, irrevocable, etc.);
- More broadly, set out some specific restrictions and limitations as to the type of contribution and content that the website is meant to host and that users are allowed to upload (e.g., not to upload any material/content that is unlawful, misleading, that generally infringes someone else’s rights). For some additional data protection considerations on this point, please see further below.

2.2.2 Success Stories

Success Stories can be considered as a news section presenting and discussing solutions used in industry or research domains. These stories are written by the Project’s Partners or are written spontaneously by the Project community. An example of a Success Story is available at the following link: <https://digiNEB.eu/success-story/digital-water-city>.

This section also includes a description of projects/movements at the EU and/or Member State level (and related external links) involved in the success story, together with some technical information (where available and applicable) on the funding of the project, the locations (e.g., city/country) that are relevant to the given project/movements, etc.

In light of the above, the considerations and recommendations expressed above in relation to the Digital Toolkit section of the website generally apply to the “Success Stories” of the website, with the following specifications:

- Content that is elaborated by the Project:
 - It is advisable that contact is established with the relevant projects/movements so as to ensure that the publication of this type of information on this section of the website is done in compliance with the Grant Agreement (in the event of an EU-funded project) or any other internal agreements that may have been stipulated by the parties involved in the given project/movement. This may be relevant in the event that those agreements establish specific obligations and limitations among the parties on the possibility of disseminating material (including summaries) that pertain to a given project/movement for communication/publicity purposes;⁴

⁴ The Grant Agreement that needs to be signed for EU-funded projects in fact contains specific rules on communication, dissemination, and visibility in particular in relation to the possibility of presenting the project (including the project summary) on websites and social media accounts: https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/aga_en.pdf (see: (i) **Article 16** at page 162 on intellectual property rights and Annex 5 at page 253 containing “Specific Rules on IPR” and (ii) **Article 17 on “Communication, Dissemination and Visibility”** at page 166 and Annex 5 containing “Specific Rules on Communication, Dissemination and Visibility” at page 276).

- The contact above would also allow the Project to duly regulate the display and posting of images/logos in this section of the website that may be protected by intellectual property rights (in particular, by seeking a specific license on the use of such material on the Project's website and in compliance with the specific conditions determined by the right holder).
- As for the content that is elaborated by third parties (e.g., website users that have set up an account on the website and wish to contribute to this section) and then uploaded in this section, similar representations as those presented in the Digital Toolkit section above should be sought from those users.

2.2.3 e-Learning

The Project presents training courses for community users in the scenarios listed below. The e-learning platform can be accessed at the following link: <https://digineb.eu/elearning-platform>

- In the case of courses hosted on external platforms, the Project includes an information sheet about the course and a link that refers to the external provider's portal for the fruition of the course;
- In the case of internally hosted courses, usable on the platform through a dedicated environment, the material may be provided by the Project's Partners or external partners free of charge.

As for the e-learning courses presented on the Project's website and yet **provided (and hosted) by third parties**, it is worth making a distinction between:

1. The relationship between the Project and the provider of the e-learning course (to which website users are redirected). As for this relationship, it is recommended that the Project enters into specific agreements (if this has not been done already) so as to regulate the possibility for the Project to display content/material/logos/trademarks and any other content that is protected under the applicable legislation. A specific authorisation for the use of such content should, in fact, be sought from the right holder, which may also set specific conditions for the use of such content in the context of the license (e.g., duration of the license, obligations around attributions, etc.). Additional contractual provisions may also be negotiated in the context of the license agreement, and that may benefit both parties, such as:
 - The respective obligations and limitation of liability (e.g., the fact that the Project will not be liable for any loss of profits in the case of "premium" e-learning courses and business opportunities more broadly);
 - Any other aspect that may be relevant to this relationship (e.g., for how long information and hyperlinks to the e-learning platform will be available on the Project's website and the discretion that the Project retains in choosing when and whether information pertaining to the relevant e-learning course is removed).
2. The relationship between the Project and its website users (that land on the website of the provider of the e-learning course through the Project's website). As for this relationship, it is recommended that the Terms of Use of the website be revised, in particular, to specify to users that the provision of e-learning courses provided by third parties (external to the Project) will be regulated by the specific terms made available by those third parties (e.g., on their website upon registration).

As for courses that are **hosted "internally"** by the Project through a **dedicated platform**, it is recommended that the following relationships be regulated:

1. The relationship between the Project and its website users (who will be able to enrol on the e-learning courses through the digiNEB platform). As for this relationship, it is recommended that a specific agreement is entered into between the Project and the website users that enrol

on a specific course so as to regulate the (sub)license that the Project grants to the website users in relation to the content itself (where this is protected by intellectual property rights), as well as any other relevant aspect that regulates the provision by the Project of e-learning course(s) to the users and the use of the platform more broadly (e.g., the use that users can make of the platform, the procedure to be followed in order to access such courses such as the need for prior registration, etc.);

2. The relationship between the Project and the provider of the material/content of the e-learning course that is uploaded on the digiNEB's platform so as to regulate the possibility for the Project to display content/material/logos/trademarks and any other content that is protected under the applicable legislation. A specific authorisation for the use of such content should, in fact, be sought from the right holder, which may also set specific conditions for the use of such content in the context of the license (e.g., duration of the license, obligations around attributions, etc.). The possibility to sub-license such content should also be envisaged in the context of this license agreement so as to ensure that this content can then be "distributed" by the Project to the website users who wish to participate in the relevant e-learning course.

2.2.4 Other considerations related to the protection of intellectual property rights

Besides the considerations expressed above (that are mainly aimed at ensuring that the publication of content/material on the Project's website does not impinge upon third parties' rights), it is also recommended that appropriate steps are taken in order to ensure that the content/material/results generated in the context of the Project are protected by choosing the most appropriate form of protection (to the extent that such content constitutes the object of copyright protection).

In this respect, it should be noted that, following some previous interactions between the External Advisor and the Project partners, especially those involved in the Ethics Board activities, some steps have already been taken in this direction. In particular, the Terms of Use of the Project's website have been revised so as to specify that the material is directly produced by the digiNEB.eu project is available under Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY 4.0) International license.

In addition to the above, to the extent applicable, due considerations should also be placed in relation to:

- Any pre-existing industrial/intellectual property rights that each of the Partners may bring to the Project, in which case the Partners would need to regulate the access rights that they attribute to the other Partners of the Project;
- Any intellectual property rights that may result from the Project, in which case the Partners should examine, in particular:
 - The possibility of protecting such results by the most appropriate means (e.g., patent, trademark);
 - Their obligations to disseminate and exploit such results (e.g., through the transfer/licensing of such results);
 - The rules/procedures to be established between the Partners to the Project on the ownership of such results (which generally depends on the party that generates those results) as well as joint ownership (in relation to the situation where two or more Partners jointly contribute to an individual result that is protected under copyright law).

For the purpose of regulating the above-mentioned aspects, the External Advisor notes that several rules aimed at governing the intellectual property aspects of the Project are already included in the Grant Agreement ("GA"), as well as in the Consortium Agreement ("CA") signed between the Project's Partners. Separate agreements can also be set up for the purpose of complementing such rules so as to regulate in greater detail some specific aspects that may arise from the Project.

3. Data Protection and Privacy

3.1 GDPR principles and their relevance to digiNEB.eu

The data processing activities inherent to the Project, which involve the processing of personal data,⁵ should take into consideration the principles set out under the General Data Protection Regulation (“GDPR”).

The main principles that shall be considered by the Project and which have been taken into consideration in the feedback that follows below include:

Lawfulness – As determined by Art. 5(1)(a) GDPR, personal data must be processed lawfully. Under Art. 6 GDPR, lawfulness requires either (i) consent of the individuals whose data is used (“Data Subject”) or otherwise some other legitimate basis, such as (ii) necessity for the performance of a contract to which the Data Subject is party or to take steps at the request of the Data Subject prior to entering a contract, (iii) a legal obligation, (iv) necessity to protect the vital interests of the Data Subject or of another natural person, (v) necessity for performing a task in the public interest, (vi) necessity for the legitimate interests of the controller or a third party (as long these legitimate interests are not overridden by the interests and the rights of the data subject). When special categories of personal data are to be collected and further processed, an applicable derogation to the general prohibition on the processing of these personal data⁶ (from those listed in Art. 9(2) GDPR, or as may be further provided under applicable member State law) must also be identified. Among these possible derogations, explicit consent could, for example, be considered (meaning that the Data Subject must give an express statement of consent).

Fairness – Processing of personal data shall always be fair (as determined by Art. 5(1)(a) GDPR), meaning that personal data shall be handled in ways that may be reasonably expected and not use such data in a way that may produce detrimental and unjustified adverse effects on Data Subjects. This principle is also strictly connected with the data protection rights that Data Subjects are entitled to exercise under the GDPR, meaning that the Project shall facilitate the exercise of these rights.

Transparency – The principle of transparency that is set out under Art. 5(1)(a) GDPR is strictly connected to the principle of fairness in that it establishes an obligation for the controller to take appropriate measures in order to keep the Data Subjects informed – in an easily and accessible way – about how their personal data will be used. This involves the development of an information notice (or privacy policy) to be provided to Data Subjects following the requirements set out under Art. 13 and Art. 14 GDPR, which prescribe the essential elements of which Data Subjects shall be informed.

Purpose limitation – As determined by Art. 5(1)(b) GDPR, personal data shall be collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes. This obligation aims to ensure openness about the purpose of the processing and to ensure that the processing activities undertaken by the controller are in line with the Data Subjects’ expectations. In compliance with this principle, the legitimate purpose(s) that the controller aims to achieve by means of a given processing need to be pre-determined (meaning that they should be determined before the design of the processing activities) and specific (meaning that the purpose[s] should be made explicitly clear to data subjects but also to other parties that may be involved in the

⁵ Article 4(1) GDPR defines personal data as “any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person (‘data subject’); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person”.

⁶ Art. 9 GDPR defines the special categories of personal data as “[...] *personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership, and [...] genetic data, biometric data [when processed for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person], data concerning health or data concerning a natural person’s sex life or sexual orientation*”.

processing, such as processors acting on behalf of the controller). In connection with the principle of data minimization (described below), the purpose will also determine what personal data is necessary for the processing.

Data minimisation – As determined by Art. 5(1)(c) GDPR, personal data shall be adequate, relevant, and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed. It follows from the above that, for each purpose of the processing activity, the controller shall identify the minimum amount of personal data needed to fulfil such purpose. In compliance with this principle, as a first step, the controller shall aim to avoid processing personal data altogether when the identified purpose can be achieved in the absence of personal data. If this is not possible, the controller shall only collect and process the personal data that are strictly relevant and necessary to the intended purpose (meaning that the purpose cannot be achieved by other means).

Accuracy – As determined by Art. 5(1)(d) GDPR, personal data shall be accurate and kept up to date so as to ensure the quality of the personal data that are collected. The controller is therefore required to ensure that appropriate steps are taken to verify the accuracy of the personal data collected, to keep those personal data up to date over time, and to provide Data Subjects with appropriate means to correct and update their own personal data, when needed.

Storage limitation – As determined by Art. 5(1)(e) GDPR, personal data shall be kept in a form which permits identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the personal data are processed. It follows from the above that personal data shall not be stored for longer than actually needed unless a reason (and a legal basis) for further processing exists. In compliance with this principle, the controller shall proceed to the erasure of personal data from its systems when it no longer has a reason for keeping them or, alternatively, anonymize and aggregate such data until the point they do no longer qualify as personal data under the GDPR.

Security (integrity and confidentiality) – As determined by Art. 5(1)(f) GDPR in combination with Art. 32 GDPR, personal data shall be processed in a manner that ensures appropriate security of the personal data, including protection against unauthorised or unlawful processing and against accidental loss, destruction or damage, using appropriate technical or organisational measures. Controllers (and processors) are therefore required to define and implement appropriate technical and organisational security measures, considering the available technology (including the state of the art and the costs of implementation), the circumstances under which personal data are processed and the risks which may result to the rights and freedoms of individuals for the purpose of ensuring a level of security appropriate to those risks.

In addition to the data protection principles identified above, some other data protection rules will need to be considered in the context of the Project. In particular, to the extent that the Project involves the use of third parties that undertake processing activities under the instructions of the controller, the controller is also subject to the obligation of verifying whether those processors provide sufficient guarantees of privacy/data protection compliance. Moreover, where the processors have been duly vetted and considered adequate in terms of guarantees offered as to privacy/data protection compliance, an appropriate agreement (commonly referred to as a “data processing agreement”) should be entered into by the controller with the processors in compliance with Art. 28 GDPR.

Moreover, to the extent that the processing activities in question involve the transfer of personal data to third countries, the provisions set out under Chapter V of the GDPR (that regulates the “[t]ransfers of personal data to third countries or international organisations”) shall also be considered so as to ensure that the level of protection afforded by the GDPR continues to “travel” with the personal data, regardless of where they land. The GDPR offers different tools to regulate the transfer of personal data outside the EU:

- Adequacy decisions, which apply where a third country has been declared as offering an adequate level of protection by the European Commission (Art. 45 GDPR);

- In the absence of an Adequacy Decision, a transfer can take place through the implementation of appropriate safeguards and on the condition that enforceable data subject rights and effective legal remedies for data subjects are available (Art. 46 GDPR) – Appropriate safeguards include, among others, standard contractual clauses adopted by the European Commission, adherence to a code of conduct or certification mechanism, and binding corporate rules that may be leveraged by a group of undertakings engaged in a joint economic activity;
- Lastly, if the personal data needs to be transferred to a third country that has not received an Adequacy Decision by the European Commission and if appropriate safeguards are absent, a transfer can still be performed by leveraging one of the derogations for specific situations as set out under Art. 49 GDPR (e.g., where an individual has explicitly consented to the proposed transfer after having been informed of the possible risks of such transfers).

The above-mentioned principles will be taken into account in order to assess the extent to which the various data points that are present on the Project website (and the processing activities conducted in the context of the Project more broadly) comply with such principles.

3.2 Considerations on registration to the Project website (creation of an account)

Registration to the Project’s website takes place via a dedicated form, i.e., “Create a new account - Join our Community”, available at: <https://digineb.eu/user/register>.

The registration form requests individuals who would like to register to the portal to provide the following information: email, name and surname, what describes them best, and “*tell us something about you*”. The form also includes a consent request tick-box to subscribe to the Project’s newsletter and tick-boxes for “acceptance” of the Terms of Use and Privacy Policy.

Below, please find relevant feedback concerning the aforementioned fields that are present in the registration form.

Create a new account - Join our Community

Email*

The email address is not made public. It will only be used if you need to be contacted about your account or for opted-in notifications.

Name*

Surname*

What describes you best?

This information is collected to understand the project's key stakeholders and tailor our offerings to better meet their needs. Your response will assist us in gathering valuable insights and ensuring that the digiNEB.eu platform aligns with the interests and requirements of our diverse user base. Please note that all information shared through this web form will be handled in accordance with our privacy policy, and your data will be treated with the utmost confidentiality and used solely for project-related purposes.

Please specify

Figure 1. First part of the registration form

Based on the form above, it is noted that the following fields are flagged as mandatory: email, name, and surname. The collection of these categories of personal information is arguably needed in order to allow users to create their account on the Project's website (which, in turn, will allow users to participate and contribute to several sections of the website, such as uploading content in the "Digital Toolkit" section of the website and participate in discussions in the Thematic Working Groups) and to receive communications/notifications from the Project. The processing of these categories of personal data is considered to pose few risks to the rights and freedoms of data subjects considering that:

- The processing activity in question is arguably based on Art. 6(1)(b) of the GDPR ("processing is necessary for the performance of a contract to which the data subject is party or in order to take steps at the request of the data subject prior to entering into a contract"), and
- The fact that only three categories of personal data (specifically, name, surname, email address) are flagged as "mandatory" is arguably in line with the principle of minimisation as the personal data in question seem to be strictly needed for the purpose for which they are collected.

As for the additional field that users can fill out by including information on what describes them best ("*What describes you best*"), it should be noted that this is marked as "optional". This entails that the registration procedure can be completed regardless of whether users choose to complete this field or not. The following considerations can be made in relation to this additional field:

- The Privacy Policy states that "[n]ot mandatory fields are used for statistical analysis and to provide more specific content". Based on this, it could be argued that the processing of these categories of personal data is not strictly needed for the "provision of the service(s)" offered by the Project. This entails that a different (from Art. 6(1)(b) of the GDPR) legal basis should be identified for the collection and consequent processing of any personal information that may be shared by users in the fields in question. The controller may, for example, base the processing of such personal data on consent (subject to considerations on whether the requirements for valid consent can be met) or legitimate interest (subject to the prior

performance of a legitimate interest assessment). These two legal bases (consent or legitimate interest) seem, in fact, to be the most appropriate grounds among those set out under Art. 6 of the GDPR, considering that (as mentioned above) this specific activity does not seem to be needed for the performance of a service requested by the user, it is arguably not needed for the compliance with a legal obligation to which the controller is subject, it is not needed either for the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority vested in the controller, and it is also not necessary for protecting vital interests of the data subjects or other natural persons. For the purpose of determining the most appropriate legal basis, it is recommended that the Project considers the level of “invasiveness” that the processing activities in question would entail. Should, for example, this additional information be used for creating “profiles” of the individuals concerned so as to better tailor the content of the communications with which users should be targeted, this should be factored into the analysis that the controller would need to carry out in order to identify the most appropriate legal basis (e.g., the controller would need to consider in the context of a legitimate interest assessment whether the creation of such “profiles” would meet the reasonable expectations of the users).

- Once an appropriate legal basis for the processing activities in question is identified, it is recommended that the Privacy Policy is updated accordingly in compliance with the principle of transparency so as to ensure that users are duly informed of the legal basis on which the processing of their personal data for this specific purpose is based.

As for the additional field that users can fill out in order to provide additional information on themselves (“Please specify”), it should be noted that this includes a **free text field** (unlike the field above that users can complete by selecting the relevant option from a drop-down menu). The use of free text fields raises the risk of collecting “unnecessary” information (meaning information that is not strictly necessary for the purpose for which this field has been made available on the registration form). In order to limit this risk, it is recommended that the controller limits the possible answers that users may give in response to the question posed or to a narrow set of options or introduce a short character limit in the field. Along the same lines, it is also recommended that additional instructions are provided to users as to the type of information that potential registrants are required to include (which would also better assist the controller in pursuing the identified purpose of processing). These instructions should also explicitly invite data subjects to avoid sharing special categories of personal data within those fields.

Tell us something about you

Only provide general info linked to your job and other activities (e.g. architect working with digital twins, built environment)

This field is provided for you to share additional information about yourself. Please note that the digiNEB.eu project is not responsible for the data shared in this field. We kindly request that you refrain from including any personal data or sensitive information, such as personal emails, phone numbers, opinions, or special categories of data under the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Your participation and submission of information through this field imply your understanding and agreement that the data shared is at your own discretion and responsibility. For more details on how we handle your personal information, please refer to our privacy policy.

Content limited to 200 characters, remaining: **200**

Figure 2. Second part of the registration form

As for the field above (“Tell us something about you”), the following considerations can be made:

- If the information that users can insert in this field is used for “*statistical analysis and to provide more specific content*” as indicated in the Privacy Policy in relation to all non-mandatory fields, the same considerations expressed above (in relation to the “*What describes you best*” section) on the importance of identifying the most appropriate legal basis (and to indicate such legal basis within the Privacy Policy) applies in relation to this section.
- Some slight rewording of the text placed at the bottom of the field is also recommended, especially in relation to the section that reads as follows: “*Please note that the digiNEB.eu project is not responsible for the data shared in this field*”. This derives from the consideration that, to the extent that the Project’s Partners act as controllers in relation to the personal data that it collects through the forms of the website, they will, in fact, be responsible – from a data protection perspective – for the lawful processing of such personal data.
- The fact that the Project has set up a word count limit and that it has included a specific warning for users not to include “special categories of personal data” should be flagged as a positive compliance action undertaken by the Project. This would, in fact, limit the risk that data subjects will share information which is arguably not needed for the purpose that this field aims to achieve. In order to further limit the risk that users insert in this field “unnecessary” personal information (which would risk placing the Project in breach of the principle of data minimisation), the Project has also added some guidance and instructions on the type of information that the Project expects from users in order to achieve the identified purpose (“*Only provide general info linked to your job and other activities (...)*”).

As a recommendation that applies to all fields above, it should be recalled that a retention period should be defined so as to ensure that personal data is not retained for longer than needed (and that users are informed of such retention periods in clear terms in the Privacy Policy). When determining such retention period(s), it is recommended that a distinction is made between the specific purpose for which the personal data are collected: the retention period of the email address that is collected for the set up of the account may, in fact, be different from the retention period that is needed for the performance of the “statistical analysis” that the Project performs on personal information included in the non-mandatory fields.

Newsletter

By subscribing to the digiNEB.eu newsletter, you agree to receive updates and information related to the development of the digiNEB.eu project. This may include data, news, announcements, and other relevant content. We use Mailchimp to distribute our newsletters. By clicking here, you acknowledge that your information will be transferred to Mailchimp for processing. [Learn more about Mailchimp's privacy practices here.](#)

Figure 3. Sign-up to the newsletter

The registration form also includes a tick-box that users can select in case they wish to subscribe to the Project’s newsletter. As for the processing activity related to the sending of the newsletter, the following considerations can be made:

- The legal basis identified in the Privacy Policy for the processing activity in question is consent (Art. 6(1)(a) GDPR). This is considered to be the most appropriate approach considering the broad interpretation that some EU data protection authorities have adopted on the definition of “marketing” communications (according to which communications that are aimed at promoting the image / the activities performed and the mission pursued by a given organisation would also qualify as “marketing” communications).
- In relation to the above, it is also worth noting that the sending of the “newsletter” is listed in the Privacy Policy under the more generic “Marketing” purpose, which includes (besides the sending of the newsletter) other types of communications for “*marketing, promotional and publicity purposes (...), market research and surveys*”. In this respect, it is recommended that

separate consent requests are collected by the Project in relation to different types of communications that the Project intends to send so that users can express a more genuine choice on the type of communications that they wish to receive: (i) the periodic and informative newsletter on the one hand, and (ii) other “marketing communications” on the other (e.g., market research/surveys, invitation to events).

- The wording provided below the tick-box should be revised in the section where users “*acknowledge that your information will be transferred to Mailchimp for processing*”, considering that:
 - Based on the information made available to the Author, MailChimp has now been dismissed in favour of a different provider (i.e., Mailjet);
 - The use of the term “transfer” may also be misleading in this case since it may suggest that personal data will be transferred outside the EU. If this is not the case (to be however verified by the Project), it is recommended that the wording is slightly rectified.
- A retention period should be defined in relation to the personal data that are collected for the purpose of delivering the newsletter. In this respect, it should be noted that, based on the information made available in the Privacy Policy, personal data for the purpose of delivering the newsletter “*will be kept by Trust-IT srl from the moment you give consent until it is withdrawn. Where it is not withdrawn, consent will be renewed at fixed intervals. Once consent is withdrawn (or not given, following a renewal), Personal Data will no longer be used for these purposes, although it may still be kept by Trust-IT srl in particular as may be necessary to protect Trust-IT srl’s interests related to potential liability related to this processing*”. The approach adopted by the controller is generally compliant with the applicable data protection principles since the possibility to renew (or not) the data subject’s consent at fixed intervals would arguably allow the controller to verify whether consent remains genuine over time. The personal data pertaining to users who choose to withdraw their consent should then be deleted by the controller unless the same data is needed for some other purposes. In addition to the above mechanism (which seems to be mainly aimed at “refreshing” users’ consent to the newsletter), it is recommended that a similar mechanism is implemented in order to ensure continuous data quality. Such mechanisms may consist, for example, in the sending of regular invitations to update subscribers’ contact details (with the consequence that if subscribers do not react, their subscription is cancelled) or in the removal from the controller’s mailing list of email addresses that the system has detected to be invalid.
- In addition to the above and in order to ensure that consent can be considered valid pursuant to the GDPR, it is recommended that the Project implements specific mechanisms that data subjects can easily leverage to withdraw (at any given time and as easily as they have expressed their consent) the consent that they have previously given without suffering any negative consequence from their choice – Considering that users can express their consent by means of a simple mouse-click (by simply ticking the checkbox the bottom of the registration form), the controller shall ensure that data subjects are able to withdraw that consent equally as easily. A similar solution seems to have been implemented by the Project since users can withdraw their consent “*by selecting the appropriate link included at the bottom of every marketing email message received*”. Moreover, it seems that registered users may also be able to withdraw their consent by logging into their personal account by “unticking” the relevant checkbox.

► Terms of Use - revision: **V1**

Terms Of Use*

Having read and I agree to the Website's Terms of use

► Privacy Policy - revision: **V2**

Privacy*

N/A

► Cookie Policy - revision: **N/A**

Manage Cookies Consents

CREATE NOW

Figure 4. Acceptance of the Terms of Use and Privacy Policy

As for the last part of the registration form, it should be noted that, at the time of writing of the present deliverable, users' acceptance to the website's Privacy Policy has been removed as previously recommended by the Author in order to avoid the risk that references to data subject's "agreement" to the content of the Privacy Policy is mistakenly interpreted as a request to express their "consent" to the processing activities described therein. At the same time, it is recommended that the checkbox that users are asked to tick in relation to the Privacy Policy ("**[] Privacy**") is clarified so that users can clearly understand what this flag would signify to the controller (in the opinion of the Author, this should generically be intended as the fact that users have read and understood the controller's privacy practices as detailed in the Privacy Policy).

3.3 Considerations on the application form as Early Adopters (and Early Adopters webpage)⁷

As for the "Early Adopters" webpage (and related registration form), two different processing activities can arguably be envisaged in relation to this section based on the information made available online and other information shared by the Project:

- The processing of personal data in the context of the registration form (which seems to amount to an "application" submitted by the applicant to the Project);
- The publication of a subset of such personal information on the Project website (in particular, the picture, job title, organisation name, short bio, and external link to the LinkedIn profile).

However, it should be noted that the Privacy Policy that is currently available online seems to only envisage one processing activity, which is labelled as "*Early Adopter Members Database*", and that consists in the inclusion of "*information on you as a registered Early Adopter within the Website pages and database*". Based on the information provided in the Privacy Policy, this processing activity is based on consent. In this respect, it is recommended that the two processing activities identified above are examined separately by the controller so as to perform a more granular assessment of the data protection considerations that these processing activities entail (and to ensure that consent, when and where request, is sufficiently granular and specific). This derives from the consideration that:

- On the one hand, the processing of personal data for the purpose of reviewing the application submitted by users as "Early Adopter" can arguably be based on Art. 6 par.1, let. b) GDPR (performance of a contract / precontractual measures), since the processing activity in

⁷ <https://digiNEB.eu/early-adopters>.

question is specifically aimed at assessing and subsequently managing data subjects' applications as "Early Adopter" (while the Project seems to have captured all processing activities connected to Early Adopter registration/application under data subject's consent). In parallel, it is also recommended that additional information is included in the Privacy Policy on the processing activity that this registration/application as "Early Adopter" entails in relation – e.g., to the evaluation that the Project will make of any such application.

- On the other hand, it is recommended that specific consent is requested from data subjects for the publication of their personal data on the Project's website (or, where consent is not feasible or would otherwise not meet the requirements for valid consent, a specific legal basis should be identified for the publication of personal information online, which seems to be a different and further processing activity from the initial processing of personal data in the context of the application/registration as "Early Adopter"). As for the publication of the picture, it is also recommended that the Project takes into account other legal requirements that, depending on the applicable jurisdiction, may regulate the use that third parties can make of individuals' images. For example, under Italian legislation, it is, in principle, forbidden to show, reproduce or profit from the reproduction of someone's image without their consent/authorisation.

In addition to the above, some other considerations can be expressed in relation to the registration form and, in particular, in relation to the steps identified in the following print screens:

The screenshot shows a registration form with the following elements:

- A dropdown menu with the text "- None -" and a downward arrow.
- Three checkboxes:
 - I allow my digital solution to be included in the NEB Digital Toolkit
 - I would like to publish a success story on the NEB Observatory about my digital solution (if you tick this box, we will reach out to you)
 - I accept digiNEB.eu's [privacy policy](#) and [terms of use](#)*
For information about our privacy practices, visit our privacy policy page.
- A CAPTCHA section labeled "CAPTCHA *" with a distorted image of the characters "9 9 7 L N C". Below the image is a text input field and the text "What code is in the image?*" with a refresh icon.
- Below the CAPTCHA, the text "Enter the characters shown in the image." and "This question is for testing whether or not you are a human visitor and to prevent automated spam submissions."
- A final checkbox: I would like to subscribe to digiNEB.eu monthly news digest

Figure 5. Early Adopters disclaimer acceptance

In particular:

- If the processing of the personal data collected by the Project for the development of the "Early Adopter Members Database" is based on consent as stated in the Privacy Policy, a specific consent form should be included in the form. As an alternative, data subjects should be informed that, by entering personal information in the various fields, they are providing their consent to the processing activity identified in the Privacy Policy (although see above for additional considerations on the importance of splitting the processing activities in question into two separate subsets).
- As for the section where users are asked to flag whether they "accept digiNEB.eu's Privacy Policy", it is recommended that this checkbox is revised since references to the data subject's "acceptance" to the content of the Privacy Policy may mistakenly be interpreted as a request to express their "consent" to the processing activities described therein.

- As for the checkbox that users can tick should they wish to “*subscribe to digiNEB.eu monthly news digest*”, if this refers to the “Newsletter” discussed above, it is recommended that reference to the “monthly news digest” is replaced with reference to the “Newsletter” to ensure consistency with the terminology used in the Privacy Policy.

In addition to the above, it should be noted that the application process also includes several free text fields. In relation to such fields, the same considerations expressed above apply (on the risk that these fields may be used to enter “unnecessary” pieces of information and how to mitigate such risks). For the sake of completeness, it should, however, be noted that the risk that these fields may be “misused” in this specific case seems to be relatively low, considering that these fields seem to be meant to include information pertaining to projects / digital solutions rather than individuals.

3.4 Considerations on the External Advisory Group webpage⁸

As for the webpage that includes the list of the individuals that compose the “External Advisory Group”, based on the information made available to the External Advisor, this list of selected individuals has been identified by the Consortium prior to the beginning of the Project. Despite the fact that decisions around the members that compose this External Advisory Group have been taken in the past, it is recommended that the Project identify an appropriate legal basis for the publication of the personal information pertaining to the individuals whose profile is displayed on this webpage. It is therefore recommended that the Project ensure that a Privacy Policy has been provided to the individuals in question and that the lawfulness of the processing activities in question has been duly assessed by the Project prior to publication of such information online. As for the publication of individual’s images specifically, the same considerations expressed above in relation to “Early Adopters” apply in this case (in particular, the consideration of the fact that the applicable local laws may impose additional requirements – besides data protection requirements – on the use of such images, such as the individual’s specific authorisation to the “economic exploitation” of their image).

3.5 Considerations on the e-Learning Module

The e-learning platform offers a catalogue of courses hosted externally or internally. In particular, the platform allows users to:

- Publish selected training material, hereby expressly including courses available on external websites (so-called “external resources”);
- Host training on the digiNEB.eu platform (so-called “internal resources”) – The possibility of hosting “internal resources” is based on the use of a customised instance of Moodle-based eLearning platform (based on Moodle 4.1.2+ www.moodle.org) deployed and freely accessible at www.digineb.eu.

The catalogue will, therefore, feature both courses available via external websites and those directly usable on the digiNEB.eu platform.

From a data protection perspective, the following considerations can be made:

- As for courses that are available on external websites (and therefore provided by third parties on third parties’ platforms), it is recommended that a specific clarification is included in the Privacy Policy in order to clarify that any processing activity performed by the provider of those courses is subject to the Privacy Policies of such third parties (since the providers of those courses are likely to qualify as controllers in relation to the personal data that they would collect in the provision of such courses).

⁸ <https://digineb.eu/eag>

- As for courses which are internally hosted and provided by the Project, it should be ensured that the Privacy Policy captures all relevant processing activities carried out by the Project and related to the registration and participation in such courses (e.g., should questionnaires/evaluation steps be included or the progress made by the users in the attendance of a given course being tracked, the performance of such processing activities should be duly reflected in the Privacy Policy in compliance with the principle of transparency and an appropriate legal basis should be identified as well). In this respect, based on the information made available to the External Advisor, third parties that upload content on the digiNEB.eu platform will not have access to information pertaining to users that will subsequently make use of that content, with the result that no relevant processing activities are arguably performed by those third parties as a result of their contribution to the e-learning platform.
- Access to training courses (whether hosted internally or externally) has been made conditional upon users' registration. This entails that, even if a course is hosted on an external website, before being directed to that website, users are prompted to create an account on the Project's website. The reason why this extra step has been added is, however, unclear, with the result that uncertainties also arise around the legal basis identified by the Project for the collection of the personal data in question.

3.6 Considerations on the Thematic Working Groups

The Thematic Working Groups ("TWG") section of the Project's website allows the provisioning of a forum space for discussions and comment feeds on the main TWG topics. The TWG, therefore, offers opportunities for collaboration, knowledge sharing, and policy recommendations. These groups allow professionals from different stakeholder groups to come together, exchange ideas, and collectively work towards advancing the NEB principles in the context of digitalisation.

The following considerations can be made from a data protection perspective:

- It is recommended that the processing activities related to the participation in the TWG be described in greater detail in the Privacy Policy to ensure that participants are made aware of the processing activities that their contribution to the discussions will entail (e.g., the fact that their username and comments will be publicly available and therefore visible to any user of the website, whether logged in or not);
- It is recommended that additional and specific instructions are added on the type of content that users are expected to include in the various comments, together with a warning about the importance of avoiding the sharing of personal information related to other individuals in the context of such discussions (unless this is deemed to be strictly necessary and subject to a specific warranty from the data subject that a lawful legal basis has been identified for the processing and sharing of such third parties' data with the Project). A similar disclaimer could, for example, be added beside the following button that users can click in order to initiate a discussion.

Figure 6. Discussion button

From a broader perspective, some additional measures could also be considered by the Project in order to discourage users from behaving inappropriately through posts, comments or other means or in a manner that is not consistent with the purpose for which the TWG has been set up. A specific notice could be set up to this aim (by revising the Terms of User of the Project’s website for example), where the Project reserves the right to delete content which does not comply with a certain series of rules (“Rules”).

An example of Rules which may be implemented follows:

“The ideas and opinions expressed by users on the various Thematic Working Groups do not necessarily reflect the ideas and opinions of the Project. The Project reserves the right to delete the following content from the discussions that may be initiated by users in the Thematic Working Groups:

- *Content which violates third-party intellectual property rights, such as materials which are protected by copyright (e.g., images, music, videos, text) or any trademarks or protected logos, save where uploaded based on those third parties’ explicit consent;*
- *Shows or performances, or parts thereof, which have been broadcast on television or streaming services, or recorded as part of a film, or otherwise published;*
- *Information plagiarised from other sources;*
- *Photographs and/or videos, including those depicting individuals, unless the subjects portrayed (and, where appropriate, the individuals depicted, or the parents or legal guardian of those individuals, where they are minors) have expressly consented to the use of those photographs and/or videos;*
- *False, inaccurate or misleading information; confidential or undisclosed third-party information;*
- *Content which amounts to threats, defamation or slander;*
- *Inappropriate statements or comments;*
- *Any text, images or other materials that may be considered as obscene, profane, vulgar, offensive, provocative or pornographic, depicting weapons, political or religious propaganda, derogatory characterizations regarding any group based on their ethnicity, race, gender, sexual orientation or religion, depicting alcohol or drug abuse or promoting illegal activities of any kind;*
- *Links to other websites; advertising; spam;*
- *Software viruses, Trojan horses, worms, time bombs or any other code or deactivation files or mechanisms designed to interrupt, damage or limit the operation of any software, hardware, telecommunications equipment or that interfere with the functioning of the Official Accounts or the social media platform.”*

Comments and content uploaded on the TWG by interacting users must be monitored with adequate frequency so as to confirm that the tone of any discussions held on such TWG remains at a courteous and non-offensive level and that any user-uploaded content (e.g., comments and replies) do not conflict with the Rules. At the same time, while compliance with the Rules that the Project will define

should be monitored and respected, it is also recommended that the Project avoid adopting an excessively rigid posture, which may create a "censorship" effect.

3.7 Considerations on registration to events/webinars

The website also includes a section where users can register for events either organised by third parties or by the Project. As for the events that are organised by third parties, such third parties will arguably bear the responsibility for the data protection obligations that arise from the processing of the personal data of participants (unless the Project is actively involved in any of the steps that lead to the collection of such personal data). In light of this (just like for the e-learning courses that are arranged and hosted by third parties that are external to the Project), it is recommended that a specific clarification is included in the Privacy Policy in order to clarify that any processing activity performed by such third parties is subject to the Privacy Policies of such third parties (which are likely to qualify as controllers in relation to the personal data that they would collect in the context of those events/webinars).

As for the events that are organised by the Project, based on the information made available to the Author, enrolment is performed through a registration form, which includes the following fields:

- Name, Surname, and Email address – These fields are mandatory for individuals to register for the event;
- *"What describes you best?"* – Following some previous interactions with the Project, this field has been marked as optional;
- *"How did you hear about this webinar?"* – Following some previous interactions with the Project, this field has been marked as optional.

As for the *"What describes you best?"* and the *"How did you hear about this webinar?"* fields, as noted above in relation to other similar cases, should these fields include a free text, there may be a risk that registrants may submit (either voluntarily or inadvertently) information that is not strictly necessary to the purposes pursued by the controller. In order to mitigate the risk of collecting "unnecessary" information, it is recommended that the controller limits the possible answer that registrants may give in response to the question posed. Based on the information made available to the Author, the Project has already included a similar disclaimer with clear instructions to guide registrants on the type of information expected and to discourage the sharing of special categories of personal data (however, as mentioned above, at the time of writing, it is not possible for the Author to verify such disclaimer as there does not seem to be any "active" registration form available online).

Moreover, and in light of the principle of purpose limitation, it should also be noted that the information that the Project aims to collect by means of the above-mentioned optional fields (*"How did you hear about this webinar?"* and *"What describes you best?"*) do not seem to be strictly necessary for the purpose of registering to the event. This may therefore suggest that such personal data may be used for additional purposes, other than the sole management of the registration and attendance to webinars / events. In light of this, the specific purpose for which such additional information is collected should be further clarified and the most appropriate legal basis should be identified depending on the purpose. If these additional (and optional) pieces of information are collected by the Project *"for statistical analysis and to provide more specific content"* as any other non-mandatory fields (based on the information provided in the Privacy Policy in relation to such fields), the same considerations expressed above in Section 3.2 in relation to the optional fields that are included in the form for the creation of an account on the website applies in this case.

It should also be noted that, following an initial interaction between the External Advisor and the Project, some changes have been made to the Privacy Policy in relation to the sections related to the organisation and registration to events. Some processing activities that were previously described in

the Privacy Policy have, in fact, been removed from the version of the Privacy Policy that is available online at the time of writing. For example, the Privacy Policy no longer refers to the fact that attendee lists will be published online based on the legitimate interest of the controller. This is deemed to be a positive amendment, especially considering that some uncertainties would arise from the use of legitimate interest as a legal basis for a similar activity (considering that the publication of attendee lists is an action that participants in an event may not reasonably expect). At the same time, it is recommended that all processing activities carried out in the context of events are duly captured in the context of the Privacy Policy. For example, should recordings be performed, and should recordings also capture personal information of event/webinar participants and/or speakers (as is the case for the project's public events, it is recommended that a legal basis is identified for such recordings and that data subjects involved are duly informed of this activity, whether in the generic website Privacy Policy or by setting up *ad hoc* Privacy Policies (to be provided to the speakers for example). This would also allow the controller to inform participants of the actions to be taken in case they do not wish to have their voice/image recorded (e.g., keeping the microphone and camera switched off). It is important to note that such information is, in any case, already always given by the event moderators when the event starts to allow people who do not wish to be recorded to leave the room.

As mentioned above, in relation to other processing activities that are carried out in the context of the Project, it is also recommended that a clear retention period is identified by the controller in relation to the personal data that is collected in the context of events/webinars. In this respect, it should be noted that no clear retention period is identified in the website Privacy Policy, which includes a generic reference to the fact that personal data processed for "Events/Webinars" "will be kept by Trust-IT "for the period deemed strictly necessary to fulfil such purposes". It is therefore recommended that the controller specifies, in a more detailed manner (where this has not been done already), for how long personal data will be kept for this purpose (and update the website Privacy Policy accordingly so that data subjects are provided with at least an indication on the timeframe within which their personal data will be deleted). Dietary preferences that have been collected in order to accommodate specific needs in the context of in-person events should, for example, be deleted right after (or shortly after) the event.

3.8 Considerations on Digital Toolkit and Success Stories

As for the Digital Toolkit and Success Stories sections of the website, it should be noted that (as mentioned above in Sections 2.2.1 and 2.2.2 of the present deliverable) both sections are meant to host content that that may be "populated" by either Project's Partners or other website users that may choose to register an account and contribute to these sections of the Project's website.

While several considerations have already been expressed above around the importance of ensuring that the publication of content in these sections does not lead to the infringement of third parties' intellectual property rights, due consideration should also be placed on data protection aspects that may be equally involved. In particular, individuals posting content should be informed that any such posts should comply with the applicable data protection principles set out in Section 3.1 above. They should furthermore refrain from posting personal data of others without their valid and freely informed consent (or other applicable legal basis), and should they decide to post such content, it must be clear to them that they are liable for any damages or claims which may be made against the controller as a result of the publication of such information. Naturally, similar considerations also apply in relation to any content that may be published by the Project itself and/or any of its Partners: before making personal data available on these sections of the website, individuals should be informed that their personal data will be processed by the controller and that it will be posted on the Project's website. The individuals concerned should also be given the opportunity to provide their consent to the publication of their personal data (where this is identified as the most appropriate legal basis) and should be fully informed of the purposes of such publication.

3.9 Other considerations on data protection aspects related to the Project's website

3.9.1. Data processing relationship with third parties that (may) access personal data collected in the context of the Project

Under the GDPR, controllers are required to only engage processors which provide adequate guarantees of privacy/data protection compliance. These processors must be engaged through a Data Processing Agreement (“DPA”), meeting the minimum requirements set out in Art. 28 par. 3 of the GDPR. In the performance of the processing activities carried out in the context of the Project, data subjects’ personal data may be shared with – at least – the following third parties (additional considerations on the role played by the different Project’s Partners are expressed further below):

- Amazon Web Services, on which the servers of the Project’s website are hosted;
- Mailjet, an email marketing automation platform that is used to deliver the newsletter to subscribers;
- Zoom Video Communications, Inc., a video meeting platform that is used to launch and host Webinars;
- Google Ireland Limited, which manages the Google Analytics that is operational on the Project’s website.

In addition to the above, some other providers may also be able to access (and therefore process) some of the personal data that are collected in the context of the Project, such as Moodle (on which the digiNEB.eu e-learning platform is based) and FLARUM (which is the software that operates the TWG pages).

Since the providers mentioned above are most likely to qualify as processor(s), it is recommended that:

- A DPA has been established with such providers, regulating the respective roles and responsibilities and indicating the instructions to be followed by them in the processing of the personal data in question. This can be done by verifying whether the DPA made available by such providers has been signed (e.g. because it is an integral part of the Terms of Service accepted by the controller when subscribing to their service/s) or whether additional actions are requested by those providers for executing such DPAs (e.g., sending a completed and signed copy of the DPA to the provider);
- The DPA signed (or to be signed) with such providers complies with all essential elements as set out under Art. 28 of the GDPR (especially when it comes to DPAs that are “unilaterally” imposed by such providers);
- It is comfortable with the privacy/data protection posture offered by these providers, particularly when it comes to data security.

In addition to the above, Section 5 of the website Privacy Policy (“*Recipients of Personal Data – Data Processors*”) should also be revised so as to ensure that it includes the full and detailed list of the entities that act as processors (Amazon Web Services is, for example, currently not listed).

3.9.2. Data processing relationship among the Project's Partners

Besides the considerations that have been expressed above in relation to the external providers/suppliers involved in the delivery of the Project, it is also worth making some considerations in relation to the relationship between the various entities that undertake a role in the management of the Project, with specific reference to the Project’s Partners.

Based on the information made available by the Project, Trust-IT acts as the “Technical Coordinator” and is also identified in the Privacy Policy as controller for the processing activities carried out through the website. In this respect, it should be noted that the privacy role of the other Partners should also

be considered to the extent that they are involved in the processing activities carried out in the context of the Project (or should they otherwise be able to access the personal data collected in the context of the Project or contribute to the determination that is made around the purposes and means of the processing activities in question). Depending on the involvement that such Partners have in the processing activities in question, they may qualify as autonomous controllers / joint controllers/processors.

Based on the information made available so far, the Partners seem to have played a role in determining the purposes and the means of the processing activities carried out in the context of the Project, although at different levels and at different degrees depending on the specific activity in question (e.g., creation of forms on the Project's website which are materially set up by Trust-IT and COMMpla after having collected the input of the other Partners, the management of Early Adopters' submissions that are materially collected by Trust-IT / COMMpla although assessed by other Project's Partners, etc.). In this respect, it should be recalled that access to personal data is not, in itself, an essential element for determining joint controllership as the focus should instead be placed on the extent to which the decisions taken by the different Partners have "converged" towards the determination of the essential elements of the processing activities in question. As clarified by the European Data Protection Board ("EDPB") in its Guidelines on 07/2020 on the concepts of controller and processor in the GDPR, *"an important criterion to identify converging decisions in this context is whether the processing would not be possible without both parties' participation in the purposes and means in the sense that the processing by each party is inseparable, i.e. inextricably linked."*⁹ This is different from the situation where an entity acts as a processor since, although processors actively participate in the processing activities in question, they do not process personal data for their own purposes (rather, they follow the instructions provided by the controller).

By applying the considerations expressed above to the specific activities carried out in the context of the Project, the following elements would arguably support the qualification of the Project's Partners as joint controllers:

- Even if some of the Partners do not have access to the personal data collected in the context of the Project (at least, not always), the Partners have participated in the overall activities conducted in the context of the Project by organising, coordinating and otherwise actively contributing to the activities of the Project, with the purpose of achieving the common goal(s) underpinning the Project which is entrusted (although at different levels and degrees) to all Project's Partners;
- (except for COMMpla – see further below on this point), it is reasonable to argue that the Partners have not performed their activities by following the instructions provided by Trust-IT and acting on its behalf (as it would be typically the case for entities acting as processors). Instead, all Partners seem to be motivated by the intention to pursue the common goal of furthering the Project's objectives;
- As for the "means" of processing, it is reasonable to maintain that, even if the development of the "digital environment" that is meant to serve as a basis for the development of the Project has been entrusted to some specific Project's Partners (Trust-IT and COMMPla specifically), this does not exclude, in itself, joint controllership when the other Partners can also play a role in determining what processing activities would be performed by means of that environment.

Having clarified the above, it should also be recalled that even if the Project's Partners act as joint controllers in relation to the processing activities carried out in pursuit of the common goals underpinning the Project, this does not entail that all of the Project's Partners would be *equally*

⁹ European Data Protection Board (2021, July 7). *Guidelines 07/2020 on the concepts of controller and processor in the GDPR – Version 2.1*. https://edpb.europa.eu/our-work-tools/our-documents/guidelines/guidelines-072020-concepts-controller-and-processor-gdpr_en, p. 19.

responsible for such processing activities. The different circumstances of the case would need to be taken into account in order to determine the respective responsibilities of the parties, which, as mentioned, may be involved at different stages and to different degrees in relation to the processing activities that are carried out for jointly defined purposes. In light of this and based on the information made available to the External Advisor, it is reasonable to maintain that Trust-IT has, in fact, played a leading role in coordinating the processing activities carried out in the context of the Project.

Where the above-mentioned conditions are met (meaning that the conditions for concluding that the Partners act as joint controllers are satisfied), it is recommended that a joint controllership agreement is established and that the Privacy Policy is amended accordingly so as to reflect the role of the different Partners are joint controllers.

Lastly, it is worth noting that different considerations may be made in relation to COMMpla, which participates in the Project as “Affiliated Entity” (in particular, as affiliated to Trust-IT). The role played by this entity seems in fact to be more in line with the role of “processor” based on the consideration that this entity seems to be mainly involved in the practical management and administration of the Project’s website based on the instructions / operational guidelines provided by Trust-IT (this latter acting in coordination and cooperation with the other Project’s Partners).

3.9.3. Transfer of personal data to third countries (outside the European Economic Area)

The transfer of personal data to third countries is subject to specific provisions (set out under Chapter V of the GDPR) aimed at ensuring that the protection offered by the GDPR travels with the data, regardless of where these are located.

In this respect, it should be noted that some of the processing activities carried out in the context of the Project would arguably entail a transfer of personal data outside the EU. Such transfers may take place either directly (where personal data are transferred to entities located outside the European Economic Area) or indirectly (where personal data are shared by the controller with entities located in the European Economic Area, which further transfer such personal data to their sub-processors located outside the European Economic Area). This is, for example, the case of Zoom (for the provision of the video meeting platform), which is based in the United States, and Google Ireland (for the provision of Google Analytics), which may then further transfer personal data collected via the Project’s website to Google LLC.

In light of this, and taking into account the most recent developments following the invalidation of the Privacy Shield by the European Court of Justice in the so-called *Schrems II* case, it is strongly recommended that the controller assess whether those transfers are covered by appropriate (and, where necessary, also by supplementary) safeguards so as to ensure that transferred personal data continue to benefit from the level of protection required under the GDPR. As for the transfer to the United States, the adherence of the “recipients” to the recently adopted EU-US Data Privacy Framework should, in particular, be verified so as to determine whether the transfer of personal data to this country can be based on the above-mentioned transfer mechanism. Google LLC has, for example, adhered to this EU-US Data Privacy Framework based on the information made available on this page: <https://www.dataprivacyframework.gov/s/participant-search>.

Where the third country “recipient” is located in a country that does not benefit from an adequacy decision, another transfer mechanism would need to be identified among those listed in Article 46 of the GDPR. At the same time, it is also worth recalling that when a transfer is based on one of the “appropriate safeguards” listed in Article 46 of the GDPR, a so-called “Transfer Impact Assessment” should also be conducted for the purpose of assessing whether the laws and practices applicable in the third country in question may prevent the data recipient from complying with the obligations undertaken under such appropriate safeguards (such as the contractual obligations under the Standard Contractual Clauses).

Moreover, the website Privacy Policy shall also be revised so as to ensure that data subjects are informed of the fact that the controller *“intends to transfer personal data to a third country or international organisation and the existence or absence of an adequacy decision by the Commission, or in the case of transfers referred to in Article 46 (...), reference to the appropriate or suitable safeguards and the means by which to obtain a copy of them or where they have been made available”* (as prescribed by Art. 13 par. 1, let. f) of the GDPR).

3.9.4. The use of cookies on the website

Based on the information made available in the Privacy Policy and in the Cookie Policy, it is noted that the website makes use of different types of cookies. After having examined the information made available in both Policies, the following considerations can be made:

- The text included in the Privacy Policy and the text included in the Cookie Policy should be better coordinated so as to ensure consistency between the two (and as a means to also avoid potentially unnecessary repetitions). For example, detailed information on the use of cookies could be removed from the Privacy Policy and replaced with a generic link to the Cookie Policy (which, in fact, does not seem to be easily accessible from the Privacy Policy);
- Both policies (i.e., the Privacy Policy and the Cookie Policy) provide that the website makes use of so-called “third-party cookies”. In order to obtain more information, users are invited to consult the privacy policies of the following providers: Instagram, LinkedIn, Twitter, and YouTube. In this respect, it is worth however noting that:
 - No link to such privacy policies is made available to users (meaning that the privacy policy of those providers is not made easily accessible to users);
 - The list of cookies indicated in the Cookie Policy does not include any cookies provided by the above-mentioned providers (Instagram, LinkedIn, Twitter, YouTube). In light of this, it is recommended that the Cookie Policy is revised so as to ensure that the list of cookies included therein is accurate and complete (and to also ensure that consent expressed by users in relation to non-essential cookies can be considered to be informed and therefore valid).
- In the sections of the Cookie Policy (and of the Privacy Policy) that explain to users the means at their disposal to manage their preferences, it is recommended that an explicit reference is made to the fact that users can, at any time, amend their preferences by means of the *“Manage your cookie preferences”* command that is placed in the footer of each domain page (besides including indications on the browser options that can be leveraged to this aim)

Some additional considerations should also be raised in relation to the two technical cookies indicated below:

consent_3rdparties_cookies	Trust-IT srl	Cookie that records if the user accepted the 3rd parties cookies	first party cookie/browsing cookie	Expires at the end of the session
consent_additional_cookies	Trust-IT srl	Cookie that records if the user accepted additional cookies	first party cookie/browsing cookie	Expires at the end of the session

Figure 7. Technical Cookies

Based on the description of the “function” / “purpose” of these cookies (as described in the Cookie Policy), these cookies are used to record users’ preferences around the use of third-party/additional cookies. These cookies are set to expire “at the end of the session”. Based on this, the External Advisor’s understanding is that the cookie banner (that presents the different options that users can select in order to express their preference on the use of cookies) will be presented to users every time they re-access the Project website so as to allow them to express their preference around the use of

cookies (since users' preferences will only be recorded by the system until the end of the previous session). In this respect, it is worth recalling that some data protection authorities have noted that the "over-repetitive" presentation of the cookie banner may be perceived by users as a "solicitation" to express their consent to the non-essential cookies installed by the website. To avoid this potential impact on user's freedom around the choice they wish to make on the use of cookies, the Italian data protection authority has, for example, recommended that the cookie banner should only be presented (again) to users after at least six months have elapsed since the cookie banner was last presented. In light of this, it is recommended that the Project reconsiders the duration of these two technical cookies mentioned above to ensure that users do not feel "compelled" to consent to the use of non-technical cookies as a result of the repetitive presentation of the cookie banner containing the request to express their consent to such cookies.

4. Ethical recommendations and compliance

This section deals with ethical concerns in relation to the Project. In general terms, it is a best practice to evaluate potential ethical issues with the aim of ensuring the integrity of the EU-funded activity. Ethical evaluations are of particular relevance in relation to projects, and in particular, those which entail the processing of personal data, as such activities have the potential to impact the rights and freedoms of individuals. Only by carrying out an evaluation of ethical impacts is it possible to identify solutions to safeguard the rights of individuals who may be impacted by a particular activity.

It should be noted that in general terms, the Project is considered to present a low risk in terms of negative impacts on the fundamental rights and freedoms of individuals. This is largely due to the nature of the Project, which is part of the Digital Europe Programme (DEP), which is “focused on bringing digital technology to businesses, citizens and public administrations”, as opposed to a Research and Innovation project, which may involve more intensive activities, especially in relation to the processing of personal data. For this reason, while it is normal practice for the External Advisor to carry out a more in-depth ethical analysis (Ethical Impact Assessment or “EIA”) using a methodology that uniquely combines the methodologies proposed by the Sienna¹⁰ and Sartori projects, together with the work of relevant scholars in the field of ethics impact assessments, an initial threshold analysis (Step 1 of the Author’s methodology) found that it was not necessary to proceed further.

The aforementioned threshold analysis involves determining if the Project under examination may design or develop technologies, policies, or protocols that may have, e.g., negative impacts on public safety or health, lead to the processing of personal data, negatively impact individual and group rights, negatively impact equality, social justice, the common good or cultural heritage, the environment and sustainable development, lead to misuse or have military purposes.

For the reasons cited above, ethical concerns are dealt with in a succinct fashion concerning relevant parts of the Project’s website, namely, the Digital Toolkit, Success Stories, eLearning, Thematic Working Groups and Early Adopters sections and the Terms of Use and Privacy Policy of the website.

4.1 Recommendations for digiNEB.eu website content

4.1.1. Digital Toolkit

As stated in Section 2.2.1, the Digital Toolkit contains what may be considered information sheets which present different “tools” that may prove useful to industry, policymakers, etc. This activity arguably poses few ethical risks. However, as suggested in Section 2.2.1, due attention should be paid to ensuring that the legal compliance issues raised are adequately dealt with. For example, it should be ensured that intellectual property rights are respected and that any necessary prior authorisations are collected, and license/sub-license agreements are entered into by the relevant parties.

From the ethics perspective, it is, as suggested in the aforementioned section, highly relevant that the Project places certain restrictions/limitations on the types of contributions and content which users can upload. Doing so will help avoid potentially harmful or unlawful content, which could lead to future ethical concerns.

From the transparency perspective, it would be relevant for visitors of the website to be able to immediately understand the nature of the content posted in the Digital Toolkit section of the website. For example, it may be relevant for the Project’s Partners to consider adding a disclaimer/text at the top of the <https://digiNEB.eu/digital-toolkit> page explaining that the page is populated with content that is developed by Project’s Partners, developed by third parties who are invited by the Project’s Partners to share their “tools”, and importantly, upon the individual initiative of third parties who independently visit the Project website and, without any invitation, decide to register and upload the

¹⁰ Brey, P. et al., Generalised methodology for ethical assessment of emerging technologies, SIENNA Deliverable D6.1, February 2021, <https://zenodo.org/record/7266895#.ZBtkVezMlq1>.

information sheets. This is because a website visitor may reasonably expect all content to be curated by the Project itself and to be, in this sense, “endorsed” by the Project.

4.1.2 Success stories

The Success Stories section of the website presents “*A unique collection of authentic narratives of EU-funded projects or initiatives that have successfully implemented digital solutions locally, while adhering to the principles of the New European Bauhaus.*”¹¹ As suggested in Section 2.2.2 of this deliverable, it is advisable for the Project to ensure that the publication of the Stories is done in compliance with any relevant agreements, including the applicable Grant Agreement. Furthermore, intellectual property aspects should be verified. As also mentioned in Section 2.2.2, it would be relevant for the Project to place certain restrictions/limitations on the types of contributions and content which users can upload. Doing so will help avoid potentially harmful or unlawful content, which could lead to future ethical concerns.

The way in which Success Stories content is drafted in terms of language should also be considered by the Project’s Partners. For example, the REMOURBAN entry (<https://digineb.eu/success-story/remourban>) shows that the REMOURBAN project ended in 2020. However, the text is drafted in the present tense, which may lead to confusion on the part of website visitors. In order to remedy this issue, the Project may wish to consider developing editorial guidelines and a quality control procedure, which would entail the verification of Success Stories from time to time.

Additionally, it should be noted that some links may bring digiNEB.eu website visitors to unsecured websites. For example, the website of the aforementioned REMOURBAN Project does not employ https, meaning that it is not secure. Furthermore, while the digiNEB.eu website does not directly link to the REMOURBAN website, users of the digiNEB.eu website may search for the REMOURBAN site after reading the entry on the Project website and accessing an unsecure link. For this reason, it is advisable that the content of the Success Stories is verified or subjected to a quality check from time to time, as suggested above.

4.1.3 eLearning

Several legal considerations highlighted in Section 2.2.3 should be dealt with to ensure, e.g., that relevant authorisations are obtained and that obligations and limitation of liability are clear and adequately regulated. In terms of ethical concerns, efforts should be made to ensure that it is clear to users that modules may be provided by third parties. For example, the Project may wish to evaluate changing the wording “by” to, e.g., “*This course has been posted and provided by [Name of entity], external to digiNEB.eu*”. Doing so may provide an additional level of transparency to website users and avoid any potential misunderstandings about the links between eLearning tools and their providers, as well as the relationship of such modules with the Project itself. Along these lines, the Project’s Partners should consider adding more descriptive text at the top of the webpage. The current text, “Collaborative online catalogue of training materials”, could be adjusted to include a descriptor which makes it clear that courses may also be hosted on external platforms.

4.1.4 Thematic Working Groups

As suggested in Section 3.6, the Project should take into consideration the level of transparency afforded to users of the website in the Privacy Policy to make it clear that their posts will be made visible to the public. Also, from an ethical perspective, it would be relevant to implement the suggestions provided in Section 3.6 to both provide for increased transparency and to discourage potentially inappropriate content.

¹¹ <https://digineb.eu/success-stories>.

4.1.5 Early Adopters

With respect to Early Adopters, the legal concerns highlighted above should be taken into consideration by the Project. For example, the Privacy Policy should be amended to contain complete information on the processing activities which take place and to ensure that valid consent is collected.

The Project should also evaluate the possibility of making such criteria known to applicants. Specifically, during an Ethics Board meeting which took place in the month of September 2023, it emerged that it is not entirely clear for all Project's Partners how the selection process unfolds. With respect to ethical concerns in relation to the Early Adopters, it would be relevant for the Project to establish objective criteria upon which the acceptance or rejection of applications is based.

4.2 Ethical Data Protection Concerns

The processing of personal data in itself brings with it multiple ethical concerns. For this reason, it is advisable that all legal data protection compliance efforts are taken by the Project to ensure not only the lawful processing of personal data but also ethical data processing. This is because, in order for data processing activities to be ethical, they must necessarily also be legal.

Of paramount concern, the Project should take into consideration the advice provided in Section 3.2 on "Considerations on registration to the Project website (creation of an account)". In particular, the most appropriate legal basis should be used to process data which is not necessary for the processing activity in question. As suggested, the determination of the most appropriate legal basis will require the Project to take into account how invasive the processing activities in question are from the perspective of the user, and any targeting should be carefully evaluated. From an ethical perspective, indeed, "profiling" and "targeting" carry significant weight due to their potential to negatively impact the rights and freedoms of individuals. Due to this fact, it is necessary that the Project also takes all necessary actions to ensure transparency in how individuals may be profiled and targeted by amending the website's Privacy Policy as appropriate.

As mentioned in the same Section 3.2, the presence of free text fields may also carry ethical implications. Specifically, the presence of such fields may lead to the collection of unnecessary personal data. For this reason, also from an ethical perspective, the Project should consider setting limitations on the types of answers which can be provided, and more detailed instructions should be given to potential registrants to reduce the risk that they provide special category data, unnecessary information (information which is not required for the identified purpose), or the personal data of others.

It should be noted that, generally speaking, marketing activities, including the sending of newsletters, are subject to a high level of scrutiny by European Data Protection Authorities. In fact, marketing is what may be considered a high-risk processing activity, necessitating that valid consent – meaning freely given, specific, informed and unambiguous – is collected from data subjects.

4.2.1. Recommendations for digiNEB.eu Terms of Use

This subsection explores ethical concerns in relation to the digiNEB.eu Terms of Use. As suggested at the beginning of this section, in order to ensure compliance with ethical principles, all relevant legal concerns raised in the preceding sections of this deliverable should first be dealt with.

It should be noted that the readability level of the Terms of Use is acceptable, meaning that the text is accessible and intelligible. However, in order to further improve readability, the Project may wish to consider providing the Terms using a more navigable approach. This would entail, e.g., developing a table of contents which is hyperlinked to the various sections of the Terms of Use such as "1. Services provided via the Website", "Events", "2. Copyright / Intellectual Property", etc.

Services provided via the website: In this section, the Project may wish to consider further specifying which services are restricted to registered users so as to improve transparency of the clause, which in

its current state leaves some ambiguity with respect to what can be seen by visitors to the site who are not registered. See, e.g., Sections 3.6 and 4.1.4 of this deliverable concerning the Thematic Working Groups, in the context of which it may not be clear that comments and usernames are visible to all website visitors.

Registered members: From an ethical perspective, the section of the Terms of Use on Registered members would benefit from further specificity in terms of the language used, i.e., what does it mean for the user to be actively involved in digiNEB.eu's work or to apply to a digiNEB.eu call? Efforts could be made to clarify this point and specifically mention how members will contribute to the Project.

Newsletters and communications: The Newsletters and communications section states that Trust-IT will send "*out informative newsletters and other communications to registered users (unless they opt out of this)*". A distinction should be made between the types of communications for which individuals must opt out. It should be noted that consent (as explained in the first half of this deliverable) is the appropriate legal basis for marketing communications, suggesting the necessity to provide the option for individuals to opt-in to any marketing-related communications.

Copyright / Intellectual Property: The legal considerations raised in the first half of this deliverable should be taken into consideration by the Project to ensure compliance with applicable legislation.

4.2.2 Recommendations for digiNEB.eu Privacy Policy

This subsection provides recommendations to improve the digiNEB.eu Privacy Policy from an ethical perspective. First, it is necessary to clarify that, first and foremost, the legal considerations presented in the previous sections of this deliverable should be dealt with as a primary concern; legal compliance and adherence to best practices in the area of personal data protection are necessary prerequisites for ethical processing. Second, while the effort to provide a hyperlinked table of contents is commendable (as has also been suggested for the Terms of Use in Section 4.2.1), the hyperlinks in the Privacy Policy do not appear to be functional. It is, therefore, suggested that they be rendered active.

As a general suggestion and best practice, having as its aim furthering compliance with the GDPR principle of transparency, the Project may wish to consider adopting transparency-enhancing techniques such as the use of data protection icons¹² and, e.g., hover-overs within its Privacy Policy. A hover-over is an example of a technique by which a specific term, e.g., "Data Subject", is made prominent, and when a user places the cursor over the term, a simple definition appears in a small bubble (the hover-over). Hover-overs provide an additional layer of transparency by allowing individuals who are not familiar with specific data protection terms to comprehend the text provided to them.

Some language issues should be resolved to ensure understandability, such as in the "*2. Personal Data processed*" section, which states, "*When you use the Website, Trust-IT srl will collect and process information regarding you (as an individual), which allows you to be identified either by itself or together with other information which has been collected.*" The same section also notes that personal data is collected from users "*simply by analysing your behaviour on the Website*". Always with the aim of promoting transparency, the Privacy Policy should be as specific as possible as to the purposes for which one's behaviour is analysed and the relevant legal basis used.

Along these same lines, the Project may wish to reconsider the phrasing of "*Personal Data which can be processed by Trust-IT srl through the Website are as follows*". Indeed, it is a best practice to use clear, plain, and precise language in privacy policies. Of specific concern here is the use of "which can," which is akin to "may". As the Article 29 Working Party suggests in its Guidelines on Transparency,¹³

¹² <https://www.maastrichtuniversity.nl/easy-privacy-information-icons-yes-you-can>.

¹³ Article 29 Working Party. (2018, August 22). *Guidelines on transparency under Regulation 2016/679 Adopted on 29 November 2017 As last Revised and Adopted on 11 April 2018*. European Commission. <https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/article29/items/622227/en>.

terms such as “may” and “might” should be avoided. Instead, affirmative terms which give the data subject a precise understanding of how their personal data will be processed should be favoured.

Under “a. Name, contact details and other Personal Data”, the Privacy Policy makes reference to “various areas of the website”. Also, in this case, the Project may wish to consider specifying the precise sections of the website which require individuals registering on the site to provide their personal data. In the same paragraph, further details should be provided about the use of personal data provided by those who register to be “used for statistical analysis and to provide more specific content”. For example, the types of statistical analyses which are carried out and the types of content and how they will be provided could be referenced in the text.

In the “d. Browsing data” section of the Privacy Policy, the Project should consider specifying the retention period for the purpose of “identif[ing] any faults and/or abuse of the Website”.

It should be observed that cookies, used to fuel surveillance and profiling, present potential risks to the rights and freedoms of individuals. First and foremost, with respect to the “Cookies” section of the website Privacy Policy, it should be noted that the hyperlinks to the Instagram, LinkedIn, Twitter, and YouTube privacy policies are not functional. From an ethical perspective, this issue should be resolved in due course to facilitate the provision of information which may be relevant to the website visitor. Furthermore, it should be noted that the website Cookie Policy¹⁴ references other cookies, such as Google Analytics cookies, which are not present in the website Privacy Policy. To this end, the Project should ensure that all cookies are served to users in the context of their browsing activities on the digiNEB.eu website is clearly disclosed. A best practice from the transparency perspective is to present a table that contains the list of all cookies used, such as that seen in Table 1. Depending on the number of cookies present, it may be preferable to develop multiple tables (e.g., a single table for each category: Strictly Necessary Cookies, Performance Cookies, Functional Cookies, Targeting Cookies).

Cookie Subgroup	Cookies	Cookies used	Lifespan
shop.digiweb.com	ABCD-TOKEN	First Party	A few seconds

Table 1. Example of a cookie table

As suggested in section 3.9.4, the Project should make reasonable efforts to coordinate the content of the Privacy and Cookie policies to genuinely put individuals in control of their information when browsing the website. Efforts should also be made to facilitate access to relevant information on cookies without requiring the visitor to search for such information. A best practice is to require users to make no more than two clicks to access relevant privacy information. To this end, as highlighted above, detailed information on the use of cookies could be removed from the Privacy Policy and replaced with a generic link to the Cookie Policy, which is not currently easily accessible from the Privacy Policy.

The Project is invited to consider combining sections 3 and 4 of the website Privacy Policy to clearly link the purposes of processing with the relevant legal basis. Doing so would facilitate users in understanding the reasons and legality behind the processing carried out by the Project. At the same time, it is recommended to provide information on the specific retention periods applied by the controller to specific data. Presenting such information together will permit website visitors and those who register on the platform to have a more complete understanding of how their information will be used. Recent decisions from European Data Protection Authorities have specifically stated that phrases such as “for the period required by the specific legal obligation or by the applicable law” are not specific enough as they do not provide any level of certainty to users about the retention of their personal data.

¹⁴ <https://digiweb.eu/privacy-policy-full>.

5. Addressing recommendations and ensuring compliance

This section summarises the recommendations provided by the External Advisor in the course of the present deliverable (as well as in the context of some previous interactions between the External Advisor and the Project). An overview of the recommendations that have been implemented so far will first be provided, followed by a summary of the main actions that still need to be implemented.

5.1. Overview of implemented recommendations at M12

Several actions have already been implemented by the Project in response to some previous recommendations expressed by the External Advisor.

In particular, in relation to the considerations expressed above on the management of intellectual property rights, as well as other (mainly contractual) considerations relevant to the Project, it should be noted that:

- The Terms of Use of the Project's website have been revised so as to specify that the material directly produced by the digiNEB project is available under Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY 4.0) International license;
- The Terms of Use have been revised so as to include (in the "Liability" clause) specific provisions in relation to third-party websites where it is specified, among others, that Trust-IT has no control over the nature and the content of those third parties websites;
- As reported in D2.2, the Project has committed to undertake several actions (as recommended by the External Advisor) in order to mitigate the risks of copyright infringements (see further below on the actions that still need to be implemented).

Moving to data protection considerations, it should be noted that:

- Some fields included in the registration forms of the website that were previously marked as mandatory are now marked as optional;
- In relation to some of the free-text fields available on the website, measures have been taken in order to limit the risk that users may "misuse" such fields by inserting information that is not strictly relevant to the purposes that the Project aims to achieve (e.g., instructions have been added on the type of information that users are supposed to include in such fields);
- The Privacy Policy has been revised so as to better clarify the description of some of the processing activities and to remove references to some activities which did not seem to be strictly relevant to the activities carried out by the Project. For example, the purpose that was identified as "Database Publication" and the purpose that consisted in the sending of email communications based on "Soft Opt-in" – which (based on the initial assessment performed by the Author) seemed to be of unclear application in the specific context of the Project – have been removed from the Privacy Policy.

Finally, further actions have been implemented as an outcome of the Y1 project review held on 6th December 2023, as described in the next paragraph.

5.2 Addressing feedback from the interim review meeting of 6 Dec. 2023

In addition to the list presented in Sec. 5.1 above, Trust-IT has worked in the past weeks to implement recommendations received by project reviewers on 6 December 2023, focussing on the following specific aspects, which the reviewers indicated as needing further improvements:

1) Modification of the privacy policy section 3 "Purposes of processing" with reference to the registrants' payment details

As requested by reviewers, Trust-IT eliminated the purpose previously listed as number 2 from our privacy policy, namely "To process your sign-up/registration forms for events and webinars hosted or

supported by the Website, process your payment details for associated fees, track event attendance (“Events/Webinars”);”. While this was initially included to open up to the possibility that some organised events may require a fee and that this would have been clearly indicated in the event description, we removed the reference altogether. No events requiring a payment from attendants were held in the first 14 months of the project. In case some will be organised in Y2, the consortium will need to update the privacy policy again to account for this occurrence.

2) Modification of the terms of use section 2 “Copyright / Intellectual Property” with reference to the use of third party material

As requested by the reviewers, Trust-IT tried to facilitate and encourage the use of material published, thus making the usage policy more user-friendly. The original text cited “DigiNEB.eu offers access to several types of content: Digital Toolkit, Success Stories, eLearning Courses, and Results of the research activities provided by third parties or produced by the project. Third parties remain owners of all the rights on the material that the digiNEB.eu Consortium only reproduces, makes available and displays on digiNEB.eu website for dissemination and research purposes. Any use of this material needs an explicit agreement with the third party owner acknowledged where appropriate. Material directly produced by the digiNEB.eu project is available under Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY 4.0) International license. DigiNEB.eu has a policy of continuous improvement of its communication and reserves the right to make improvements or changes to the online content without notice”.

While the above formulation was agreed with and approved by the External Advisor of the project, the revised text clarifies that general use of the materials as presented in the website is allowed without additional permissions, while more specific or personalised uses can be addressed by contacting the relevant third-party providers shown in the website. As such, the updated terms of use, that are currently published at www.digineb.eu, state: “digiNEB.eu offers access to several types of content: Digital Toolkit, Success Stories, eLearning Courses, and Results of the research activities provided by third parties or produced by the project. These materials, sourced from third parties or created by our project, are readily accessible for your information and research needs. For third-party content, while the original owners retain all rights, you can freely use the materials for research and dissemination as presented on our site. For more specific needs or personalised uses, please contact the respective third-party providers, who are duly acknowledged alongside the content. Material directly produced by the digiNEB.eu project is available under Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY 4.0) International license. DigiNEB.eu has a policy of continuous improvement of its communication and reserves the right to make improvements or changes to the online content without notice”.

5.3 Future plans and next steps

As reported also in D2.2, the Project has identified additional actions (as recommended by the External Advisor) – that are yet to be taken – in order to mitigate the risks of copyright infringements (see further below on the actions that still need to be taken), such as:

- Seeking the necessary authorisation from the right holder prior to publishing any material/content on the Project’s website that may be protected under copyright law and/or by seeking reassurances and representations from third parties (that upload material on the website) that they have the right to post/upload such content and that such content does not violate the intellectual property rights of third parties (as well as third parties’ rights more broadly);
- Entering into specific agreements with all parties involved (in particular, with website users and with the providers of the material for the e-learning courses) so as to regulate the licensing/distribution of any content subject to copyright as well as the platform usage more broadly;

- With specific reference to the “Digital Toolkit” and “Success Stories” sections of the website (although similar considerations also apply to the TWG section as reiterated below), defining specific restrictions and limitation as to the type of contribution and content that the website is meant to host and that users are allowed to upload (e.g., not to upload any material / content that is unlawful, misleading, that generally infringes someone else’s rights).

Moreover, it is also recommended that appropriate steps are taken in order to ensure that the content/material/results generated in the context of the Project are protected by choosing the most appropriate form of protection (to the extent that such content constitutes the object of copyright protection). As mentioned above, in relation to this specific point, due account should be given to the provisions already set out under the GA and the CA.

From a data protection perspective, the following (main) recommendations have been expressed:

- A specific legal basis should be identified for the processing activities that the Project intends to carry out “*for statistical analysis and to provide more specific content*”;
- Additional measures should be adopted in order to limit the risk that “unnecessary” information is shared by users in free-text fields (e.g., in relation to the “*Please specify*” field that is available in the registration form for setting up an account);
- Some additional recommendations have also been expressed in relation to the sending of the newsletter, such as the need to update the check-box that users can tick for signing up for the newsletter (in particular, by removing any remaining references to MailChimp) and the importance of setting up different consent requests depending on the type of communications that the Project intends to send (one for the newsletter, which tends to have more informative content, and one for other – more strictly speaking – “marketing communications” such as the invitation to participate to certain events);
- Some recommendations have also been expressed around the checkboxes where users are required to acknowledge the content of the website’s Privacy Policy (in particular, in order to remove reference to the user’s “acceptance” of the Privacy Policy by replacing it with a more generic request from the user to confirm that they have read and understood the website Privacy Policy);
- As for the application that individuals can submit as “Early Adopter”, it is recommended that the Project draws a line between (i) the processing of personal data that is performed for the purpose of assessing the application submitted and (ii) the processing of personal data that consists in the publication of personal information pertaining to the selected “Early Adopters” – This would allow the Project to identify the most appropriate legal basis for these two processing activities and to enhance transparency in the Privacy Policy by providing a more detailed level of information on the processing activities in question;
- As for the “External Advisory Group” webpage, it is recommended that the Project has identified an appropriate legal basis for the publication of the personal information pertaining to the individuals whose profile is displayed on this webpage (and that the individuals in question have been informed of the processing activities performed by the relevant controller in relation to their personal data in compliance with Article 13 of the GDPR);
- As for the e-Learning Module, it is recommended that the Project ensures that all processing activities are duly captured in the website Privacy Policy (and that an appropriate legal basis is identified for any such processing activity). As for e-learning modules that are hosted externally (i.e., on third parties’ websites), it is recommended that the website Privacy Policy specifies that any processing activities that may be performed in relation to those modules (once users are re-directed to those third parties’ website) fall under the data protection policies adopted by those third parties (the same applies to external events/webinars to which users are directed when browsing the “Events” section of the website). The reason why users

are prompted to create an account (or to log into their account) for the sole purpose of being re-directed to the third parties' website should also be clarified;

- As for the discussions in the TWG, it is recommended that the processing activities that the participation in such discussions would entail be more clearly stated in the Privacy Policy (e.g., by including a reference to the fact that the username and associated comment will be visible to any user that visit the website). From a broader perspective (by taking into account considerations that also go beyond data protection-related concerns), it is also recommended that some "rules" are set out so as to discourage the "inappropriate" use of TWGs through posts, comments or other means that may not be consistent with the purpose for which the TWGs have been set up (notably, similar rules should also apply in relation to the Digital Toolkit and Success Stories sections of the website so as to avoid that personal data of others is "unlawfully" made publicly available on these sections);
- As for the registration to webinars/events, it is recommended that the Project ensures that all processing activities carried out in the context of the events/webinars are duly captured in the website Privacy Policy (and that an appropriate legal basis is identified for any such processing activity), such as in relation to any recording activity that may be performed;
- Clear retention periods should also be identified (if this has not been done already) in relation to all processing activities carried out in the context of the Project, and the Privacy Policy should be edited accordingly so that individuals are given at least an indication of the timeframe within which their personal data will be deleted;
- It is recommended that the data processing relationship between the controller and the various entities acting as processors (to which some of the processing activities carried out in the context of the Project are delegated) is duly regulated and that the compliance posture of those entities is verified. Likewise, it is also recommended that the data processing relationship between the Project's Partners is duly revised and formalised in light of an actual and factual analysis of the influence that the different Partners play in relation to the processing activities carried out in the context of the Project (in particular, by entering into a joint controllership agreement so as to regulate the respective responsibilities in relation to the processing activities that are the result of a "joint" – although not necessarily equal – determination of the parties);
- It is also recommended that the controller verifies that all data transfers (where performed directly by the controller or indirectly by the processors engaged by the controller) are grounded upon a valid data transfer mechanism and that the Privacy Policy is revised so as to ensure that data subjects are informed of the fact that the controller intends to transfer some of their personal data outside the European Economic Area (and of the transfer mechanism on which such transfers are based);
- The Cookie Policy and Privacy Policy should also be revised in relation to the information on the cookies deployed by the website so as to ensure: (i) consistency between the information included in the two documents (the Cookie Policy on the one hand and the Privacy Policy on the other), (ii) the completeness and accuracy of such information, and (iii) that the recording of users' preferences around cookies is in line with the latest guidelines expressed on the matter by the EU data protection authorities.

From an ethical perspective, the following suggestions have been provided, which frequently mirror the legal concerns expressed:

- Ensure that all legal compliance recommendations are adequately addressed by the Project's Partners;
- Establish restrictions/limitations on the types of contributions and content which users can upload to the website, also by establishing character limits for free text fields to avoid the publication of inappropriate content;

- Establish editorial guidelines for parts of the website that individuals can edit and/or a process in which content is regularly reviewed by the Project's Partners;
- Consider adding disclaimers at the top of certain pages, such as the Digital Toolkit and Training pages, to provide further context and transparency to website visitors about the origin of the content displayed;
- Amend the website Privacy Policy to ensure all statements are accurate and include, among others, information for individuals populating the TWG page so they are aware that their posts can be viewed by the public; complete information on data processing activities to ensure the acquisition of valid consent where necessary; detailed information on profiling and targeting activities; specific information on the services provided by the website to not leave any ambiguities (i.e., avoid the use of "may", "might", etc.); adequate and accurate information about cookies served via the website; a clear link between the purposes of processing and the legal bases relied upon to improve the level of transparency provided by the website;
- Establish and follow objective criteria for the evaluation of Early Adopters.

Finally, as the project is well into its Year 2, it is crucial to reconvene the **Ethics Board** at the earliest convenience, firstly to re-assess and re-structure it, particularly in response to the departure of Trust-It and COMMpla from the project, but, most importantly, to continue addressing the ever-evolving scenario defined by the growing digiNEB.eu community.

The intervention of the Ethics Board in Years 2 will have to revolve around the work agenda that will be prioritised with the active support of the Ethics External Advisor. This step is essential to ensure that the Ethics Board continues to function effectively and efficiently (considering also the strict budget constraints provided by the Project), guaranteeing the project's commitment to ethical standards and guiding the project towards its objectives with integrity and responsibility.

6. Conclusions

This document provides a detailed analysis of the primary intellectual property, data protection, and ethical concerns inherent to the digiNEB.eu Project.

A number of legal and ethical aspects to be addressed following the first 15 months of the project life have been identified and practical solutions or implementation trajectories have been suggested. Several improvements have been already been implemented in Year 1, including modifications directly stemming from the Y1 project review, whereas other steps will be tackled in the period January through September 2024.

As noted above, the Project's activities pose limited threats to the rights and freedoms of individuals from an ethical perspective. However, due attention must be paid to legal compliance aspects which have been explored in detail, as lawfulness represents an essential precondition for ethical compliance. To this end, particular attention should be paid to ensuring compliance with the principles of lawfulness, fairness, and transparency as they are represented in the GDPR under Art. 5(1)(a), and efforts should be made to implement all relevant considerations provided in sections 2 and 3 of this deliverable.

Given these considerations and the upcoming departure of Trust-It and COMMpla from the project, it is important to reconvene, restructure, and re-launch the Ethics Board in Year 2. This will ensure continued vigilance over potential legal and ethical issues, as advised by the External Ethics Advisor. The Ethics Board meetings will serve as an ideal platform for monitoring and implementing necessary measures.

A final ("Year 2") version of this report will be prepared in September 2024.

7. References

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/5/ Court of Justice of the European Union. (2014, February 13). *The owner of a website may, without the authorisation of the copyright holders, redirect internet users, via hyperlinks, to protected works available on a freely accessible basis on another site* [Press release]. <https://curia.europa.eu/jcms/upload/docs/application/pdf/2014-02/cp140020en.pdf>.

/6/ Court of Justice of the European Union. (2016, September 8). The posting of a hyperlink on a website to works protected by copyright and published without the author's consent on another website does not constitute a 'communication to the public' when the person who posts that link does not seek financial gain and acts without knowledge that those works have been published illegally [Press release]. <https://curia.europa.eu/jcms/upload/docs/application/pdf/2016-09/cp160092en.pdf>.

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/8/ European Data Protection Board (2021, July 7). *Guidelines 07/2020 on the concepts of controller and processor in the GDPR – Version 2.1*. https://edpb.europa.eu/our-work-tools/our-documents/guidelines/guidelines-072020-concepts-controller-and-processor-gdpr_en.

/9/ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation).